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Table of Contents

1 Introduction.....	5
2 From the Library Toolkit to HORTUS: how the Toolkit Libraries for WP3 evolved into an integrated research platform.....	5
2.1 The Beginning – A Shared Toolkit.....	5
2.2 From “Reusable OSS Software” to Building a Real Platform.....	5
3 A microservices architecture at the service of research.....	6
4 A completely new application layer.....	6
5 How HORTUS orchestrates the needs of the Work Packages.....	7
5.1 WP3 – T-ReS (GNORM).....	7
5.2 WP2 – Infrastructure and AAI.....	7
5.3 WP4 – DaMSym; WP6 – YASMINE; WP7 – REVER; WP8 – uBIQUity.....	7
5.4 Publication, citability and reuse.....	8
6 Conclusion: What Changes for Researchers and Improvement with Respect to a Simple Library.....	8
7 Final Summary.....	9
8 Applicable documents.....	10
9 Reference documents.....	10

List of Tables

NON È STATA TROVATA ALCUNA VOCE DELL'INDICE DELLE FIGURE.

List of Figures

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1 Introduction

This whitepaper was meant to describe the software specification of shared components useful across the WPs of the ITSERR project. Due to the nature of the project and its history, this deliverable developed from a simple specification for software libraries into an enlargement of the ITSERR objectives, with the identification of the need for a common ITSERR marketplace (HORTUS) that will host the tools developed in each WP.

2 From the Library Toolkit to HORTUS: how the Toolkit Libraries for WP₃ evolved into an integrated research platform

2.1 The Beginning – A Shared Toolkit

In 2023, when we defined the initial idea of the ‘library of common components’ for Work Package 3, ITSERR staff invested three months of structured research to truly understand the cross-cutting needs of the various WPs. This was made possible by the Platform Design Thinking training period that involved all ITSERR researchers, not just those from WP₃.

Following this training, researchers from each WP adopted a Platform Design Toolkit / Ecosystemic Thinking approach (together with Design Thinking) to map actors, value flows, capabilities and “minimum viable interactions” between research groups. This resulted in a shared list of reusable functionalities that cut across scientific fields and are flexible enough to withstand the evolution of use cases.

This analysis phase confirmed the original mandate of WP₃ – T-ReS: to create a toolkit/library of software components for religious studies (CRITERION, GNORM), capable of maximising synergy between WPs and accelerating the development of robust, secure and scalable tools. The description of T-ReS itself explicitly refers to a “library of reusable components”, designed precisely to simplify and speed up development and to be reapplied in other WPs.

2.2 From “Reusable OSS Software” to Building a Real Platform

However, research and analysis regarding the sharing of tools and components between the ITSERR project WPs highlighted the need to make a more ambitious choice than that envisaged in the project. Instead of limiting WP₃ to a “catalogue” library of open-source components and packages, we associated and incorporated the infrastructure needs of WP₂ (storage, computing, Identity & Access Management, hosting/presentation of results) in order to transform that list of components into an integrated research platform: HORTUS (HOsting Religious sTudies Services).

The logic was simple: the requirements gathered in 2023 with researchers (cross-cutting functionalities useful to all) + the infrastructure needs of WP₂ (data centre and AAI services) = a cohesive environment where researchers and tools can coexist natively. In other words, the library “emerged” as a platform: a single place that exposes components as services, connects them with federated authentication/authorisation, offers storage/collaboration, publication and discovery, computing power and analysis, and a site (portal) to showcase projects and results. This direction is perfectly aligned with the vision of WP₂ (Data Centre Services: AAI, storage, compute, hosting, marketplace, security) and the functional/technological framework defined for ITSERR.

3 A microservices architecture at the service of research

HORTUS was designed as a modular system, in which each microservice manages a well-defined set of functions — identity, storage, publishing, collaboration, communication, training — interconnected via secure and interoperable APIs.

The technological foundations are inspired by D4Science infrastructures (AAI, Workspace, Catalogue), but each component has been redesigned, customised and integrated into a new ecosystem. Among the main elements developed or significantly evolved are:

- Identity & Access Management (AAI) with Single Sign-On, roles and identity exchange towards Virtual Research Environments (VRE) and services, in order to orchestrate roles and permissions for users and project groups.
- Workspace for secure, versioned storage, quotas, rich metadata, persistence and integration with social/catalogue—the everyday environment for collaborating on data and documents (private, shared or VRE).
- Catalogue/Publication Platform (based on CKAN + business services) to publish resources with persistent identifiers, licences, extensible metadata, immutable payloads and standard APIs (including DCAT/OAI-PMH), even directly from the Workspace.
- Integrated social/news/notification for posts, threads, mentions, news, messaging and notifications—community and dissemination tools at the VRE/project level.
- VRE and computing/analytics services (DataMiner, orchestration, import/publish of software/algorithms) to provide processing time and AI-as-a-Service to the tools of the various WPs.

4 A completely new application layer

All of HORTUS' end-user features — from the workspace to publishing and community management — have been developed from scratch, building a modern, modular software layer on top of the basic services inspired by D4Science.

The result is a system in which microservices work together to offer:

- **AAI and customised role management**
integrated with research federations and controlled by an internal policy and permissions system.
- **Storage and collaboration**
through a flexible and secure workspace, with versioning, metadata and advanced sharing.
- **Publication and presentation of results**

with an extensive, customised catalogue that manages all types of research objects (documents, data, models, software, images, 3D, etc.), and a web portal for project visibility.

- **Communication, events and training**

through community tools, the Training Centre and integrated news and event management.

- **Visualisation and interoperability**

thanks to dedicated viewers and integration with open standards, ORCID, DOI, and FAIR schemes.

All these services were tailor-made for researchers, based on the results of user experience analysis and interactive prototypes validated in tests. The goal was not to replicate existing tools, but to build a new operating environment modelled on real research, publishing and interdisciplinary collaboration processes.

5 How HORTUS orchestrates the needs of the Work Packages

5.1 WP₃ – T-ReS (GNORM)

HORTUS fully meets the needs of WP₃, which originally aimed to build a library of common components for research tools. Instead of simply collecting reusable software, HORTUS translates that vision into an ecosystem of specialised and integrated microservices.

For the CRITERION and GNORM projects, the platform provides federated identity management (AAI), secure storage with versioning, GNORM application hosting, and customisable project metadata.

5.2 WP₂ – Infrastructure and AAI

WP₂ forms the operational basis of the entire HORTUS platform. All microservices dedicated to researchers are based on this infrastructure: AAI, role management, distributed storage, computing and hosting services, security, backup, and API integrations with external services.

In addition to providing essential technological resources, WP₂ supports the orchestration of microservices, ensuring consistency between authentication, authorisation, and access to the various modules.

The Training Centre, built on Moodle, was also developed from this base, enabling the continuous training of the ITSERR community with courses, tutorials, and personalised paths linked to active projects.

5.3 WP₄ – DaMSym; WP₆ – YASMINE; WP₇ – REVER; WP₈ – uBIQUity

These Work Packages required the processing, management and publication of corpora, linguistic models and executable pipelines. HORTUS provides Virtual Research Environments (VREs) built as

autonomous microservices, offering computing power, provenance management, AI-as-a-Service software integration and automated publication of results (datasets, models, scripts).

Each output is associated with extensive metadata and a DOI, ensuring full compliance with FAIR principles. Grobit visualisation capabilities and other integrated 3D viewers allow interactive exploration and representation of the data produced, while the notification and subscription system allows researchers to follow projects, topics or resources of interest, receiving updates in real time.

5.4 Publication, citability and reuse

HORTUS integrates an advanced publication catalogue, developed specifically to manage a wide variety of scientific artefacts: documents, datasets, models, code, images, videos and 3D models. Each resource is accompanied by enriched metadata, transparent licences (e.g. CC BY 4.0 for derivative products) and persistent identifiers (DOI).

Through the Expert Database, researchers can define their scientific profile, link ORCID and DOI, automatically import their publications and share results, plugins, datasets and software tools. All application modules — from the workspace to the publication manager — have been developed from scratch, based on detailed mock-ups and UX analyses conducted with research groups.

The system communicates natively with GitHub and Zenodo, enabling automatic citation, traceability and distribution of results according to FAIR principles.

Thanks to integration with ORCID, each author retains full ownership of their work and can synchronise personal and bibliographic data without duplicating information.

The communication components — event manager, news manager, community channels and real-time notifications — ensure the dissemination of results and the building of a lively, participatory and interconnected community.

6 Conclusion: What Changes for Researchers and Improvement with Respect to a Simple Library

- **A single place to work and publish**

Users log in with their account (AAI), collaborate on Workspace, launch analyses or AI services in VRE, publish on Catalogue (with DOI, licence, metadata), communicate with news/social media and present the project via the portal. Everything is tracked, versioned and ready for citation/reuse.

- **Heterogeneous formats and payloads, no vendor lock-in**

PDFs, images, sources, 3D, tabular or geospatial datasets, scripts and models: HORTUS manages them as resources with metadata and persistence, making it easy to reuse other people's work or build new pipelines on existing results.

- **Security, roles and governance**

Granular roles, public or moderated VREs, private/shared/VRE folders, licence and sharing controls, backup and recovery—all while maintaining openness (Open Science) where possible.

- **From component to service**

The “components” of the WPs exist as services that other WPs can invoke (e.g., a 3D viewer from WP9-Taurus), accelerating the composition of solutions without duplication.

7 Final Summary

- With Platform/Ecosystemic Design, we have identified a shared set of functionalities necessary for all WPs.
- The entire ITSERR team has integrated the infrastructure needs of WP2 and transformed the WP3 library into HORTUS, a research platform that provides IAM, storage/collaboration, computing/analytics, publishing, community and portal services.
- Operational aspect: services and results are tested/UAT, compliant with the Definition of Done, managed via issue management, versioned and published on GitHub/Zenodo with open licences.

Thus, the initial need for a “library of common components” generated HORTUS: not just a catalogue of reusable pieces, but a living platform that combines infrastructure, tools and community, truly synergising the Work Packages of religious studies research.

(End of Document)

